

INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF THE CLUSTERING SYSTEM OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

Shoira Karshiboyeva Sindarkulovna

Assistant at the Yangier branch of the Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology. Subjects to be taken - Introduction to management, macro- and microeconomics, economics and business management, engineering economics

Annotation: In article, features of realization of innovative pedagogical technologies are considered. A feature specified of use of interactive forms of education. Dynamics revealed of introduction of innovative technologies is. The research conducted is of use of interactive forms of education and information and communication technologies. The interactive nature and effectiveness of use in educational practice and education of innovative technologies reveals.

Keywords: innovative educational technologies, innovative cluster method, interactive tutoring, information and communication technologies.

From an educational point of view, the meaning of the term “Cluster” is clearly defined. However, a large number of existing definitions are almost always understood by the educational community as one and the same (and even the concentration of different English and Russian terms is almost the same). The features of innovative education, that is, the combination and use of joint resources, as well as the results of scientific research and professional activities to improve quality, serve to develop the effectiveness of education and the activities of educational institutions in general.

Let's look at innovations in improving educational technologies and, accordingly, what innovative technologies are. It is important to understand that innovation is associated with the creation of all kinds of innovations and is a

process of implementation. The use of a certain method in the environment of development of educational technologies in universities means entering the sphere of something new, placing it in it and creating a whole series of changes. The innovative cluster method not only improves operational efficiency, but also optimizes the management system.

The main advantages of introducing the cluster approach in higher education institutions:

- development of cooperative relationships with cluster participants, including university professors and teachers and students;
- formation of a modern cooperative mentality in society when conducting scientific and research work;
- free exchange of information, formation of a unified information space;
- formation of mobility of participants in academic development and research processes (exchange of scientists, masters, students, that is, integration into a single educational space);
- consider the effective use of the best available scientific and research work;
- allows you to increase the volume of scientific work, expand it, develop the commercialization of scientific foundations, and introduce socially significant products into practice.

In the cluster method, the student or reader is forced to search because one needs to know something in order to write words related to a number of topics. So, this method encourages the student or reader to learn on his own. The advantage of the cluster method over other methods is that all knowledge on a topic is collected in a heap, and depending on this group, the topic is revealed. Below are some points to consider when implementing the cluster method.

Familiarize yourself with the rules for forming a cluster. Write the title of the topic with keywords in the center of the chalkboard or piece of paper. It

ensures the activation of knowledge, helps to freely and openly introduce new associations into the process of thinking on a topic.

Clustering is the grouping of studied objects according to the similarity of their properties. Each cluster contains similar objects, but they differ significantly from the objects included in other clusters. Dividing a set of objects into clusters makes it possible to identify patterns and knowledge, propose new hypotheses, and evaluate the information content of the properties of objects. The use of a large number of indicators in the clustering process leads to the fact that the selected clusters do not have a clear structure, therefore clustering was carried out only according to the main indicators of universities.

The cluster as a mechanism for innovative management of the development of the higher education system makes it possible to ensure the effectiveness of the activities of each educational institution included in it, including: the development of social partnership, attracting extra-budgetary funds into the education system. sphere of education, the emergence of resources for innovative training, retraining and advanced training of teaching staff, new high-quality educational results based on the continuous development of the child, make it possible to improve the image of institutions. A special place in the innovative development of regions is occupied by state classical universities, which play the role of integrators of professional education, science and culture of the region. A classical university, located in the center of the unique educational space of the region, not only fulfills an educational mission, but is also the most important social institution that can be used to form and influence the innovative infrastructure of the region.

In conclusion, I would like to emphasize that education is never isolated, and scientists, masters, and students develop it together. The development of society, the country, the world has a direct impact on the existing social situation. Procedures and mechanisms for training and retraining of personnel go back to higher education institutions. Higher education institutions are one of the

foundations that lay the foundation for scientific progress and joint development of science. It is necessary to recall that responsibility for the quality of the implementation of the cluster falls on each teaching staff working at the university. It should be noted that cluster analysis is a very convenient tool that makes it easier to perceive a large number of differences.

List of used literature:

1. Boymurodov A.Kh., Azimkulov S.N., Davlatova A.R. (2021). ADVANTAGES AND OPPORTUNITIES OF THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM. Academic Research in Educational Sciences, 2(11), 1389–1395.

2. Boymurodov A.Kh., Azimkulov S.N., Davlatova A.R. (2021). ADVANTAGES AND OPPORTUNITIES OF THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM. Academic Research in Educational Sciences, 2(11), 1389–1395.

3. Rakhmatov F.A., Nursaidov N.Yu., Azimkulov S.N. (2019). ANALYSIS OF PROBLEMS OF ORGANIZING THE DOCUMENT EXCHANGE PROCESS IN MEDICAL INFORMATION SYSTEMS. INNOVATIVE IDEAS IN THE CREATION OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES AND SOFTWARE, 1(41), 196-198.

4. Seytov A.J., Khurramov A.J., Azimkulov S.N., Shcherbaev M.R., Kudaibergenov A.A., Khasanova S.Kh. (2021). Optimal control of operating modes of pumping stations of the Karshi main canal cascades. International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Engineering and Technology, 8(4), 17177-17185.

5. Sindarkulovna, K. S. (2023). ALOQA XIZMATLARI KO'RSATISH TIZIMINING MAMLAKAT YALPI ICHKI MAHSULOTDAGI ULUSHINI OSHIRISH. PEDAGOGS jurnali, 33(2), 37-39.

6. Sindarkulovna, K. S. (2023). KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIK KORXONALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA INNOVATSION MARKETINGDAN FOYDALANISH YO'LLARI.

PEDAGOGS jurnali, 33(1), 161-163.

7. I.Tishabayeva, Z.Xatamova, N.Ibragimov, O.Xamdamova. (2023). O‘ZBEKISTON TARIXI FANLARINI O‘QITISHDA ZAMONAVIY PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH MASALALARI. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IDEAS IN MODERN EDUCATION, 1(7). Retrieved from <http://woconferences.com/index.php/SIIME/article/view/690>

8. Xamdamova O.M., Xatamova Z.N., Ibragimov N., Tishabaeva I. (2023). O‘ZBEKISTON TA‘LIMIDA UZVIY BOG‘LIQLIK VA RIVOJLANTIRISH USULLARI. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IDEAS IN MODERN EDUCATION, 1(7). Retrieved from <http://woconferences.com/index.php/SIIME/article/view/689>

9. Ибрагимов, Н. (2023). РАЗВИТИЕ СИСТЕМЫ КАЧЕСТВА ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В РЕГИОНАЛЬНЫХ ВУЗАХ ДЛЯ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ИХ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ. Conference on Digital Innovation : "Modern Problems and Solutions". извлечено от <https://fer-teach.uz/index.php/codimpas/article/view/1091>

10. Ибрагимов, Н. (2023). РОЛЬ СТРАТЕГИЧЕСКОГО ПЛАНИРОВАНИЯ В ПОВЫШЕНИИ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ РЕГИОНАЛЬНЫХ ВУЗОВ. Conference on Digital Innovation : "Modern Problems and Solutions". извлечено от <https://fer-teach.uz/index.php/codimpas/article/view/1116>

11. Ибрагимов, Н. (2023). СТРАТЕГИИ МАРКЕТИНГА В ПОВЫШЕНИИ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ РЕГИОНАЛЬНЫХ ВУЗОВ. Conference on Digital Innovation : "Modern Problems and Solutions". извлечено от <https://fer-teach.uz/index.php/codimpas/article/view/1069>

12. Ибрагимов, Н. (2023). УПРАВЛЕНИЕ КАЧЕСТВОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ ДЛЯ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ РЕГИОНАЛЬНЫХ ВУЗОВ. Conference on Digital Innovation : "Modern Problems and Solutions".

извлечено от <https://fer-teach.uz/index.php/codimpas/article/view/1068>

13. Ибрагимов Наврўзбек Кимсанбаевич, Рустамов Илхомиддин Абдуқодирович, Хатамова Зумрадхон Назиржоновна, Бурхонов Илёсхон Муҳиддинович. (2023). ОЛИЙ ТАЪЛИМ МУАССАСАЛАРИНИ РАҚОБАТДОШЛИГИНИ БОШҚАРИШДА БИТИРУВЧИЛАРНИ ИШ БИЛАН ТАЪМИНЛАШ МАСАЛАСИ. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IDEAS IN MODERN EDUCATION, 1(7). Retrieved from <http://woconferences.com/index.php/SIIME/article/view/688>

14. Ibragimov, N., & Kimsanbayev, A. (2023). DAVLATGA IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKNI ZARURLIGI: RAQAMLASHTIRISH VA TAHIDDLAR. Research and Implementation. извлечено от <https://fer-teach.uz/index.php/rai/article/view/796>

15. Ibragimov , N., Nabiyev , I., & Abduqodirov , A. (2023). IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKNI TA'MINLASH VA UNI HAR TOMONLAMA RIVOJLANTIRISH. Research and Implementation. извлечено от <https://fer-teach.uz/index.php/rai/article/view/793>

16. Ибрагимов, Н. (2023). РОЛЬ ИННОВАЦИЙ В ПОВЫШЕНИИ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ РЕГИОНАЛЬНЫХ ВУЗОВ. Conference on Digital Innovation : "Modern Problems and Solutions". извлечено от <https://fer-teach.uz/index.php/codimpas/article/view/1067>

17. Ibragimov Navro'zbek Kimsanbaevich (2023). THE ISSUE OF EMPLOYMENT FOR GRADUATES IN IMPROVING THE MECHANISM OF COMPETITIVENESS OF REGIONAL HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8415277>

18. Ибрагимов, Н. (2023). ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ ИНФОРМАТИКИ В УЧЕБНЫЙ ПРОЦЕСС ВУЗА: МЕТОДЫ И ПОДХОДЫ. Conference on Digital Innovation : "Modern Problems and Solutions". извлечено от <https://fer-teach.uz/index.php/codimpas/article/view/1067>

teach.uz/index.php/codimpas/article/view/1103

19. Ибрагимов, Н. (2023). РАЗВИТИЕ КРИТИЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ СТУДЕНТОВ В ТЕХНИЧЕСКИХ ВУЗАХ. Conference on Digital Innovation : "Modern Problems and Solutions". извлечено от <https://fer-teach.uz/index.php/codimpas/article/view/1566>

20. Ибрагимов, Н. (2023). ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ АКТИВНОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ В ТЕХНИЧЕСКИХ ВУЗАХ. Conference on Digital Innovation : "Modern Problems and Solutions". извлечено от <https://fer-teach.uz/index.php/codimpas/article/view/1567>